

Democratizing energy markets through flexibility-based demand response optimization services

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ABSTRACT

Today, the energy system is largely driven from the perspective of suppliers and only a few consumers are able to track their energy use or actively participate in the market. The possibilities for larger commercial and industrial consumers have started to develop and active consumer engagement in Demand Response programmes is gaining traction, nevertheless this is not the case for residential consumers. While the participation of European residential and small commercial/industrial users, accounting for ca. 70% of final electricity consumption, there is still limited access from the end users in energy markets. Within this context, we present an end-to-end Automated Demand Response Optimization Framework, towards incorporating innovative and highly effective tools to enable dynamic VPPs formation which will further allow for energy customers and cooperatives to introduce themselves in energy markets. Optimization in the proposed framework applies to multiple levels. It spans local generation output, demand and storage flexibility, as well as the flexibility offered by EVs (in their dual role as demand and storage assets) to facilitate maximum RES integration into the grid, avoidance of curtailment and satisfaction of balancing and ancillary grid needs. The overall framework is tested in several demo sites in Europe and the preliminary results from this evaluation process are reported in this document.

INTRODUCTION

Since the liberalisation of the energy sector in Europe, significant developments have taken place, including growing competition and market integration, decreasing wholesale prices, and the enhanced uptake of renewable energy sources. Nevertheless, and even though consumer empowerment has become a buzzword in European energy policy, options and benefits for consumers have so far remained limited [SEDC, 2018]. Today, the energy system is largely driven from the perspective of suppliers and only a few consumers are able to track their energy use or actively participate in the market. The possibilities for larger commercial and industrial consumers have started to develop and active consumer engagement in Demand Response programmes is gaining traction, nevertheless this is not the case for residential consumers. While the participation of European residential and small commercial/industrial users, accounting for ca. 70% of final electricity consumption, there is still limited access from the end users in energy markets [JRC, 2017]. On the other hand, residential buildings comprise a huge source of flexible energy demand and storage considering the current E.U. trend for mass integration of local RES and battery systems; further enabling the provision to the distribution and transmission system operators, the needed services to balance demand & supply and manage power quality.

The E.U. vision is to place prosumers at its core and enable them to take ownership of the energy transition, benefit from new technologies to reduce their bills, participate actively in the market and to protect them from economic vulnerabilities. Putting this vision into practice requires a radical shift in energy market and business model design. Collective schemes are a natural candidate, for example energy cooperatives that can ensure the required market openness and transparency for making demand response a viable and attractive business case for all involved stakeholders [RESCoop, 2015]. Energy cooperatives currently have limited participation in energy markets, which limits their potential to exploit the flexibility they possess (generation, demand, storage) and the value it holds for all involved stakeholders. Apart from the legal and regulatory barriers present in different Member States, energy cooperatives are also faced with business and technological shortcomings to introduce their microgrids as active balancing and ancillary assets in energy markets. New business models, accompanied by clearly defined and transparent rules, standardized contracts and appropriate

technological tools, need to be defined to allow energy cooperatives to undertake the role of the aggregator and offer the huge flexibility potential of their prosumers/members (mainly residential prosumers) in energy markets. The rapid proliferation of energy cooperatives around the E.U. (over 2,400 cooperatives representing more than 1 million prosumers) [RESCoop, 2017], along with the regulatory framework that progressively favours the introduction of collective schemes in the E.U. energy market, create a unique business opportunity for energy cooperatives and their transition to an aggregator business model. This can pave the way for the effective share of smart grid benefits and give prosumers the power to benefit from their active participation in a democratized energy market.

In response to the aforementioned challenges and needs, we introduce an end-to-end Automated Demand Response Optimization Framework to enable the realization of novel business models, allowing energy cooperatives to introduce themselves in energy markets under the role of an aggregator. The idea is to provide cooperatives with innovative and highly effective tools for the establishment of robust business practices to exploit their microgrids and dynamic VPPs as balancing and ancillary assets toward grid stability and alleviation of network constraints. The overall architecture for the proposed framework is presented in Section 2. In Section 3, the modeling principles about the integrated flexibility approach are presented while in Section 4, the business perspective of the proposed framework is analyzed along with the preliminary demonstration activities performed. In the last section, the main conclusions and next steps are presented.

AN END-TO-END DEMAND RESPONSE OPTIMIZATION FRAMEWORK

In order to facilitate the active participation of prosumers in innovative energy management schemas as the one proposed in this paper, the definition of a concrete and transparent architecture of the proposed framework is required. The proposed demand response optimization framework contains three high level functional constituents which are further broken down at different deployment levels. These are (i) the Interoperability and Secure Big Data Management Layer, providing technical and semantic/ syntactic interoperability across the DR value chain using widely adopted open standards, (ii) the Demand Response Optimization and Control Dispatch DSS Layer deployed both at the building and district level and incorporating a variety of functions (local/building level and district level) to support optimal decision-making, and (iii) the Visualization Platform and End-User Toolkit Components Layer encompassing front-end applications that will be made available to all stakeholders involved in the proposed framework. The high-level overview is presented in Figure 1 with the details of the main components of the architecture to be further analysed.

Figure 1 An end-to-end Demand Response Optimization Framework

At the first layer, the **Interoperability and Big Data Management Framework** comprises the backbone for all integration activities in the proposed schema. It consists in an open and semantically enhanced infrastructure enabling open-standards-based interoperability and data exchange across the Demand Response value chain. The Interoperability and Big Data Management Layer couples two main technological offerings to ensure seamless integration, communication and operations among the different business entity, namely: (a) a local building gateway enabling end-to-end interoperable communication between the different applications at cloud level and individual smart home devices along with the required local intelligence (Local Demand Managers) in order to perform in real time building level decisions for the operation of the different controllable devices. (b) a centralized platform enabling ensuring fine-grained and interoperable communication and data exchange with a variety of heterogeneous sources (buildings, district DER management systems, business actors' systems and mass treatment and storage of huge volumes of heterogeneous data sets.

At the second layer, the **Demand Response Optimization and Control Dispatch DSS Framework** is responsible to incorporate the business logic and deliver high-level demand response strategies to be deployed over appropriately selected prosumer clusters. This layer consists of (a) the Global Demand Managers to define appropriate consumer clusters that can effectively participate in Demand Response events, based on their defined flexibility and response capability to multi-variate DR triggers for the provision of different services to the grid and to continuously monitor the evolution of the Demand Response event so as to, optimize business functions and energy transactions. Complementary to this a (b) Flexibility Forecasting, Segmentation and Aggregation Engine is responsible for the multidimensional analysis, correlation and efficient management of prosumer profiles, flexibility and response capacity to DR signals to enable the dynamic and spatio-temporal segmentation for the selection of appropriate aggregated demand side-based VPPs. The module will constantly interact with the (c) DER registry which is responsible to discover new DERs and invoke innovative matchmaking algorithms for aggregators to find the best DERs for their service request.

At the top layer of the proposed framework, the **Business and Visualization Layer** integrates and appropriately configures the different business applications to deliver a fully-fledged suite of services and user interfaces to the end-users, namely: (a) Energy Cooperatives/ Aggregators for optimal portfolio management, flexibility segmentation, classification and clustering, dynamic VPP formulation, self-consumption (within microgrid boundaries) and DR strategies implementation monitoring. (b) Prosumers for increased awareness and understanding on consumption patterns and flexibility potential. The coordination of the different actors is performed through the establishment of an open demand flexibility marketplace.

The definition of the architecture is provided in a fully scalable and extendable way, exploiting the concept of micro-services to enable the definition and design of different business services for the business stakeholders. In the following section, the focus is about presenting the algorithmic details for the demand flexibility modeling and optimization framework that consist of a core part of the proposed architectural schema.

A HOLISTIC FRAMEWORK FOR BUILDING LEVEL DEMAND FLEXIBILITY ANALYSIS

Towards enabling the demonstration of the end to end DR optimization framework, a better understanding of the modeling approach for demand flexibility is required; as an anchor point of the **Demand Response Optimization and Control Dispatch DSS Framework** presented in Section 2. In this section, an innovative demand flexibility framework is presented. The main pillars for the innovation are (a) the incorporation of several building level device types in a unified modeling framework and (b) the adaptation of human comfort preservation framework for demand flexibility. Then, business visualization tools are defined for the demonstration of the different business services are presented.

Establishment of a human comfort preservation demand flexibility management framework

At first, the way to incorporate the different DERs is presenting, further providing the details for flexibility modeling of the different flexible DERs. The next figure (Fig. 2) is providing an overview of the holistic flexibility framework in a

building environment. Details for the modeling capabilities of each specific flexible load follow.

Figure 2 A Holistic Framework for Building Level Demand Flexibility Analysis

The selection of the aforementioned flexible devices/concepts for modeling is delivered based on the following principles:

- Total consumption per load in building premises and flexibility potential
- HVAC and lights modeling with focus on human comfort preservation
- Virtual Energy Storage as a candidate for innovative power to heat concepts
- Electric vehicles with high consumption, capacity and flexibility potential

The modeling principles for each specific segment of the analysis are presented taking into account that:

- Models should be - to the extent possible – **simple** and **scalable** in terms of accuracy, complexity, etc.
- Models should follow a **data-driven approach** using “internal” configurable parameters
- Models should **rely on as little information** as possible for training/calibration and output estimation / obtainable using measurement devices of acceptable cost and intrusiveness

The main idea behind the analysis is the definition and further incorporation of human context parameters in the modeling framework. “Context is any information that can be used to characterise the situation of an entity: a person, place, or”. In this section the focus is on the extraction of human context taking into account information related to **events from user behaviour and respective comfort preferences**, along with information about environmental context/ conditions, towards defining robust and dynamic demand profiles, which will lead to the delivery of Context-Aware Load Flexibility Profiles, reflecting real-time demand flexibility as a function of multiple parameters, such as time, device operational characteristics and individual/group occupant comfort preferences. Building context (environmental conditions and user preferences and needs) environment is the driving force for operation of devices (from building occupants) and towards this direction, we define and further incorporate these specific building dynamics as part of the Device Flexibility models.

Comfort Modelling and DER Demand Flexibility

A non parametric, Bayesian based model network is used for extracting personalised comfort models. The input measurements required for the estimation of the comfort profiles are the following:

- Environmental conditions, namely temperature, humidity and luminance measurements.
- Heating/Cooling/Lighting control actions, notifying any changes in the operating status of devices, triggered by the occupant.
- User comfort preferences, informing on changes in comfort boundaries, made by the occupants

The details of this framework are available through [Tzanidakis et al., 2017]. Following the definition of the comfort boundaries for the users (as part of the thermal comfort model analysis), we incorporate them in the DER optimization

framework. The main objective of an optimisation framework is to provide the required control inputs such that:

- The cost of operation for the device source is minimized or maximised
- The device operation should be based on the typical operational characteristics.
- All comfort constraints of the system must be satisfied.

For the 2nd point, the operational constraints of each device type should be incorporated in the modeling principles. The proposed optimization framework consists of a model-predictive control (MPC) algorithm, which makes use of a model of the dynamical system to predict its future evolution in order to optimize the control signal for a given time horizon in the future. Details of the optimization framework are out of the scope of this paper [Tzanidakis et al., 2017]

Virtual Energy Storage towards Power to Heat demand flexibility

Virtual or Thermal Energy Storage is an innovative framework exploiting the thermal storage capabilities of existing domestic water heaters and building spaces (building thermal inertia) to dispatch desired amounts of flexibility without compromising occupant comfort or disrupting daily routines and operations. The approach introduced in FLEXCoop utilizes existing untapped storage capacity of buildings leveraging a cost-effective and highly efficient virtual thermal storage solution exploiting building capacity to store energy in their thermal mass or existing water heating equipment. From a commercial viewpoint, several VTES systems are available in the market enabling control of water heating and space heating/ cooling loads and thus there is a high potential for incorporating logic for the optimal control of these device types. The analysis is twofold: (a) for thermal inertia of the building, the analysis is performed on the basis of the HVAC modeling as presented above. The main expansion of the model is to incorporate building behaviour parameters (e.g. building inertia factors) in order to optimally balance the operation of HVAC devices with the technical and operational limitations from the performance of building as an active organization. For Domestic Hot Water Heaters, the approach is differentiated as we have to incorporate model specificities like (a) hot water usage profiles, (b) inlet/outlet water temperature (c) power profile of a DHW heater. A second-degree parameter function is considered for modeling DHW operation; once defined we can further incorporate grid/market constraints towards defining the optimal demand shifting related strategies.

Electric Vehicles as flexible loads in the grid

One of the main innovations of the proposed framework, is the incorporation of the electromobility in the integrated approach, considering the wide adoption of EVs in the near future. The idea is to present the appropriate models for accurate and robust profiling of EV flexibility in the framework of both G2V and V2G programs. The presented models should be constructed in such a way towards enabling the definition of individual EV profiles taking into account dynamic parameters such as driving patterns, distance that needs to be covered, state of charge of EV batteries, discharge rates, etc. There are two main pillars considered for the EV modeling work:

- Accurate EV profiling on the basis of the different parameters affecting the profiling process, namely: availability at the charging points (start time, end time, duration, SoC at start time, SoC at end time etc.
- Accurate EV flexibility profiling on the basis of EV availability, controllability potential over the different EV types/charging points (technical and operational limitations), grid and market needs

As the overall framework for EV flexibility profiling is multidimensional affected by multiple parameters, a local optimization process is considered in order to define the series of control strategies (EV optimization schedules) that have to be incorporated in the holistic DSS optimization framework.

Generation RES Profiling and Control

Another main innovation of the proposed framework, is the incorporation of RES as part of the holistic management framework. The main scope is twofold: (a) to ensure the physical integration with the RES controllers and (b) to provide accurate models that will facilitate short forecasting and control of RES entities in a coordinated framework. For the former, an extensive analysis has been performed to evaluate the different standards in the field. While high heterogeneity in the field, there are some standardization bodies and initiative promoting standardized approach. Special remark to the

Sunspec Alliance focusing on Inverter-based device integration based on MODBUS protocol. A non-exhaustive list of IT services and control parameters are specified in order to enable monitoring of real time production and fine-grained control (reactive power limitation, active power control, battery management etc...) of the inverter. The incorporation of local RES in self consumption schemas mandate for the extraction of high accuracy RES profiles. Mid term (day ahead) and short term (next 4 hours) RES forecasting profiles are calculated taking into account weather/metrology data and historical RES data (either from the same unit or from another RES in the same region). Incorporating accurate RES data in the energy management framework, we proceed with the holistic optimization of the different system entities.

Demand Optimization and Control Dispatch DSS

By presenting the detailed flexibility model principles for each specific load type, the integration of load flexibility in a holistic management framework follows. For the optimization process we take into account:

- The types of DR services available in the market
- The flexibility potential of the different device types (availability, capacity, response time etc...)
- Other contractual/business/operational constrains apply during the optimization process

This holistic approach is presented in Figure 3. The flexibility potential of the different device types is incorporated in the optimization engine along with contextual constrains (environmental conditions, device operation, market data) that set the boundaries for the optimization process.

Figure 3 Holistic Demand Optimization and Control Dispatch DSS [FLEXCoop D3.5, 2018]

The different phases/steps of the optimization process are further defined:

- Assets ranking and 24h forecasts where the DER filtering and prioritization takes place in order to define the potential of flexibility for further exploitation
- Optimization process where it is triggered once a DR request is delivered. Based on the results of the ranking process, the elicitation and final selection of best fitted assets takes place in order to address DR signal specific requires
- Signaling and monitoring as the last step of the optimization process where the actual control commands are triggered and a loop feedback is requested in order to deliver the dynamic adaptation of the optimization to address DR signals specific requirements.

It is evident that a fully dynamic approach is adopted for the optimization process, incorporating the multiple model parameters in the holistic framework. The overall process is performed in a sequential way in order to ensure that the initial analysis of flexibility leads to the decision-making process followed by a continuous monitoring of the overall DSS performance. The timeframe for this analysis is adaptable in order to address the different energy market and grid needs and requirements.

Definition of the Business Layer and End-User Toolkit Layer

Along with the definition of the modeling layer for demand flexibility optimization, we consider supportive business tools in order to facilitate demand flexibility business exploitation. There are 2 main business applications presented in this paper (a) a blockchain enabled demand flexibility marketplace and (b) end user visualizations for Residential/ Tertiary Consumers/ Prosumers. The scope of this section is to provide the details about the functionalities & features supported by each business application.

A Blockchain enabled Demand Flexibility Marketplace

The main objective of the proposed framework is to offer the utilities a variety of online services addressing specific needs for the overall coordination of the business strategies, and more specifically in their tasks of continuous analysis of consumers’ behavioural dynamics, configuration, planning and roll-out of efficient demand response strategies, continuous impact & performance evaluation as well as necessary re-design and corrective actions. For that reason, an automated framework needs to be established to facilitate the active enrolment of end customers in different business campaigns defined by the demand side aggregators.

Such a marketplace should be accessible by both prosumers and aggregators and arbitrated by local DSOs. Aggregators should publish their offers to attract consumers and engage them in flexibility services. Alternative contract types and remuneration methods (both for standby and activated DERs) should be offered to prosumers, who will be given the opportunity to further negotiate and customize their contractual relationship with aggregators not only in economic terms, but also regarding contract duration, number of DER activations, frequency of control dispatch, flexibility sharing, etc. Once an agreement is established, prosumers will automatically provide access to the respective DERs which will be further semantically updated to reflect the contractual terms agreed between the aggregator and the prosumer, which will be reflected in a Smart Contract Mechanism (blockchain-enabled). Details of this contractual mechanism is presented in Figure 4.

Figure 4 Blockchain for Demand Flexibility Marketplace

Taking into account the list of requirements and the supported features, indicative business usage scenarios are defined for the flexibility marketplace in order to first compile the list of different functionalities in a unified framework and further enable a dynamic, plug and play and fully automated process for the different business actors. More specifically, the

platform may be considered as a useful tool for Aggregators & Prosumers in order to continuously monitor their performance in terms of EPC, while the same platform with some adaptations could act as a tool for retailers in order to facilitate their daily business associated with customers performance under different energy key performance indicators.

A User-Friendly Application for Prosumers/ Consumers

This is the complement UI tool to engage end customers towards their active participation in different energy market schemas and business models within the context of the deregulated energy market environment. In order to enable their active engagement, the main features and functionalities to be supported are among others energy demand monitoring and analytics, demand forecasts as extracted from analytics services, notifications of demand response events triggered by aggregators and verification of compliance with contracts, smart controls and automation overriding options, along with a rich analytics dashboard for increasing awareness around energy consumption and demand response (e.g. comparison with similar peers, previous periods analytics, DR convenience and strategy overriding metrics, etc.). The overall development of the UI tool is performed in line with the business framework of the proposed concept, as presented above with the definition of the energy marketplace. A component-based application development is followed in order to address the different functionalities as specified above. Screenshots from the Business App for the prosumers are presented in the following figure (Fig. 5).

Figure 5 Energy Application for Prosumers/ Consumers

A key component of the proposed business concept is the alignment to demand data with generation/ storage capabilities in business premises. Thus, the web application for the end users is defined as a tool to support the demonstration and further evaluation of innovative self-consumption schemas.

EVALUATION OF THE PROPOSED FRAMEWORK AND PRELIMINARY RESULTS

Following the definition of the main dynamics for the proposed framework, the extended evaluation takes place in four large scale pilot sites. Validation will be performed in the cooperative microgrid of SomEnergia in Spain. SomEnergia is Spain’s largest renewable energy cooperative with over 31,000 members. The cooperative was founded at the end of 2010 and has achieved phenomenal growth since then. It currently grows with a rate of about 1,500 new customers per month. SomEnergia currently provide 44,000 households and small businesses – 13,000 of which are commercial customers, not members - with renewable electricity and we expect to surpass the 50,000-customer milestone within 2019. At the surrounding of the small village of Heeten in Netherlands, the cooperative Endona is having a solar project with 5,000 solar panels. Moreover, it has obtained exemption from the legally regulated electricity tariffs as aforementioned in order to freely conduct research experiments. Therefore, the installation of smart equipment for demand side management seems a great opportunity for the local community; thus, the evaluation of the proposed framework. In Austria, the overall framework

will be tested in a local microgrid in Gussing, the most innovative small grid in Europe. Finally, in Sorea, France, a pilot testbed will be established in order to further evaluate the impact of regional RES and local flexible demand under a coordinated management framework

A total number of 100 users have been selected for the evaluation of the proposed framework. Activities to be performed count for the installation and demonstration of smart equipment, definition of viable business models, validation of the technical solution and then a 12-month period full evaluation of the proposed framework. Some screenshots from the initial installations took place are presented in Figure 6.

Figure 6 Demonstration Activities for the Holistic DSM framework: (a) SomEnergia Demo Site, (b) ODE Demo Site, (c) EV DSS Lab Demo Site

It is evident that the evaluation of the proposed framework will try to engage end customers and business stakeholders (DSOs, aggregators, retailers etc..) and will integrate different types of device types (EVs, RES, Batteries, CHP units, building premises) along with their flexibility capacity in order to ensure the prompt validation in actual conditions. The overall evaluation process will span in the whole range of activities as specified above: end users contractual, business market participation, actual management of flexibility, settlement and remuneration.

CONCLUSIONS AND KEY REMARKS

The energy management process in buildings heavily relies on three interrelated factors: building characteristics, business and operational processes & occupants' preferences. In this paper we have presented a holistic flexibility management framework that incorporates the heterogeneous factors in a unified framework. This is the user centered demand flexibility management framework that presents the ability for integration of different data sources in real time and further management on the basis of the organizational specific characteristics in order to extract accurate demand flexibility profiles. Along with the presentation of the overall methodology and the modeling of the main system components, the business perspective for the stakeholders and the initial validation activities are presented.

Our plans for future work consist in the validation of the proposed framework over a long period of time followed by appropriate optimizations: a) evaluation of the proposed framework in different energy communities focusing on business cases and demonstration scenarios b) further expansion of the framework to address additional load types and incorporate additional energy services and analytics features in the platform. Furthermore, our future plans include the development of an enriched visualization toolkit that will complement the existing features as supported by the current version of the different apps.

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NOMENCLATURE

DR	=	Demand Response
EV	=	Electric Vehicles
VPP	=	Virtual Power Plant
RES	=	Renewable Energy Sources
DSS	=	Decision Support System
DER	=	Distributed Energy Resource
MPC	=	Model Predictive Control
HVAC	=	Heating, Ventilation, Air Conditioning
VTES	=	Virtual Thermal Energy Source
DHW	=	Domestic Hot Water
G2V	=	Grid to Vehicles
V2G	=	Vehicle to Grid
DSS	=	Decision Support System
DSM	=	Demand Side Management
DR	=	Demand Response
DSO	=	Distribution System Operator

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